

ims

“BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH VA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT”

Xalqaro ilmiy haftaligi

28-31-may 2025 yil, Toshkent,
O‘zbekiston

International scientific week

“SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND GREEN ECONOMY”

May 28-31, 2025 y., Tashkent,
Uzbekistan

Tashkent 2025

Dear colleagues, partners, and esteemed guests,

It is with great pleasure and deep respect that we welcome you to the International Scientific Week on “Sustainable Development and Green Economy” held at the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology.

This year’s event is particularly significant, as it coincides with the nationwide declaration of 2025 as the “Year of Environmental Protection and Green Economy” in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The event reflects a growing commitment—both national and global—to tackling environmental challenges, promoting sustainable development, and fostering innovation in green technologies. The International Scientific Week has become a tradition that unites academic and industrial communities to exchange knowledge, promote research collaboration, and support the integration of sustainable practices in science and industry. It serves as a vital platform for dialogue on how science, particularly chemistry and chemical engineering, can drive solutions to the pressing challenges of our time.

Uzbekistan’s chemical sector is undergoing a transformation, prioritizing advanced technologies, environmentally responsible production, and global partnerships. In line with this national momentum, scientific institutions are working to train a new generation of engineers and researchers capable of contributing to sustainable industrial growth. The Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology plays a key role in this transition by fostering academic excellence, international exchange, and innovation-led education.

Participation in this Scientific Week offers a valuable opportunity to explore and address shared challenges in sustainability—from climate change mitigation to clean energy, circular economies, and resource-efficient manufacturing. The contributions made here will help shape the vision for a greener future, grounded in scientific excellence and technological innovation.

Let us remind ourselves of a simple yet profound truth:

We need chemistry to realize the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

We need chemistry to combat poverty.

We need chemistry to improve health.

We need chemistry to mitigate climate change.

We need green, inclusive chemistry that respects our planet and serves all of humanity.

We extend our heartfelt welcome to all participants and wish you a productive, insightful, and inspiring week of scientific exchange.

Sincerely,

Prof. Botir Usmonov

Rector of the Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology

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O‘ZBEKISTONDA MILLATLARARO MUNOSABATLAR VA BAG‘RIKENGLIK

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O‘zbekiston mustaqilligining dastlabki yillaridan boshlab, jamiyatda millatlararo totuvlik va bag‘rikenglikni ta‘minlash davlat siyosatining asosiy yo‘nalishlaridan biri sifatida belgilangan. O‘zbekistonda 130 dan ortiq millat vakillarining manfaatlarini muvofiqlashtirish va ular o‘rtasida totuvlikni saqlash taraqqiyotning muhim omilidir. Ushbu yo‘nalishda millatlararo munosabatlarni rivojlantirish, har bir millatning tili, madaniyati va an‘analarini saqlash hamda ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sharoitlarni yaxshilashga qaratilgan keng qamrovli islohotlar amalga oshirildi. Buning natijasida yurtimizda do‘stlik, birdamlik, tinchlik va barqarorlik muhitining shakllanishi, amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlarning samaradorligini oshirish hamda O‘zbekistonning xalqaro maydondagi obro‘-e‘tiborini yanada yuksaltirishga muhim turtki bo‘ldi.

Millatlararo munosabatlar va bag‘rikenglikni ta‘minlashning huquqiy asosi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi, milliy siyosatni muvofiqlashtiruvchi qonunlar va normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar, shuningdek, xalqaro huquqning demokratik tamoyillariga asoslanadi. Bugungi davrda, milliy jarayonlarning mohiyatini tushunish va yosh avlod tarbiyasida millatlararo munosabatlarni uyg‘unlashtirish metodlarini ishlab chiqish, shuningdek, bag‘rikenglikni oshirish masalalari benihoya muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Barchimizga ma‘lumki, O‘rta Osiyo mutafakkirlari Abu Nasr Farobiy, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Alisher Navoiy, Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur va jadidlarning asarlarida Turkiston mintaqasida yashovchi barcha xalqlar o‘rtasida hamjihatlikni ta‘minlash zarurligi ko‘rsatilgan va tolerantlik g‘oyalari ilgari surilgan.

Millatlararo bag‘rikenglik juda teran ma‘noni aks ettiradi. Millatlararo bag‘rikenglik bu barcha millat va elatlarning teng huquqlilik, o‘zaro hurmat va hamkorlik asosida tinch-totuv yashash g‘oyasidir. Bu g‘oya millatchilik va fashizmga qarshi turadigan, barcha millatlarning tili, urf-odati, an‘analari, bayramlari rivojlanishini talab etadi. Prezidentimiz ta‘kidlaganlaridek, “Xalqimizning etnik, madaniy va diniy sabr-bardoshi ma‘naviy uyg‘onishning yana bir bitmas-tuganmas manbaidir. Ming yillar mobaynida Markaziy Osiyo g‘oyat xilma-xil dinlar, madaniyatlar va turmush tarzlari tutashgan va tinch-totuv yashagan markaz bo‘lib keldi. Etnik sabr-toqat, bag‘rikenglik hayot bo‘ronlaridan omon qolish va rivojlanish uchun zarur tabiiy me‘yorlarga aylandi... Ayni shu zaminda ko‘p asrlar mobaynida jahon madaniyatlari dunyo miqyosida bir-birini boyitgan”[1]. Xaqiqatan xam, turli konfessiyalarga mansub fuqarolarning O‘zbekiston zaminida birgalikda hamnafas va hamjihat bo‘lib yashashi diniy-ma‘naviy totuvlikning nodir timsoli va barcha din vakillariga nisbatan bag‘rikenglikning eng yaxshi namunasi deb hisoblanishga asoslidir. Mamlakatimiz aholisining 80 foizini o‘zbek, 4,9 foizini tojik, 3,8 foizini rus, 3,6 foizini esa qozoq millatiga mansub kishilar tashkil etgan. Jami 130 dan ziyod millat va elat vakillari orasida islomdan tashqari xristianlik, yahudiylik va buddaviylik dinlariga e‘tiqod qiluvchilar ham bor[2].

Yurtimizda adolatli milliy siyosat olib borilgani ko‘p millatlilik maqsadimiz yagonaligini, taqdirimiz birligini, hamjihatlik zarurligini tushunishta yordam beradi, umuminsoniy g‘oyalarning ustuvor bo‘lishini, shaxsiy manfaatlarini to‘g‘ri anglab olishni osonlashtiradi. Aksincha, milliy munosabatlarga ziyraklik va noziklik bilan yondashmaslik umummilliy tamoyillarga biroz e‘tiborsizlik ham tinchlik va barqarorlikka salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatishi mumkin. Xususan, qomusimizning 18-moddasida barcha fuqarolar bir xil huquq va erkinliklarga ega bo‘lib, jinsi, irqi, millati, dini, ijtimoiy kelib chiqishi, e‘tiqodi, shaxsi va ijtimoiy mavqeidan qat‘iy nazar, qonun oldida tengdir»[3], - Bularning barchasi shuni anglatadiki, davlat va uning organlari hamda sudlar barcha fuqarolarni bir

xil asosda, bir xil huquq va erkinliklar bilan ta'minlashi shart. Hech kim ushbu belgilari tufayli kamsitilmasligi kerak.

2017-2021 yillarda O'zbekistonni rivojlantirish harakatlar strategiyasi beshta ustuvor yo'nalishining aynan beshinchi bandi «Xavfsizlik, millatlararo totuvlik va diniy bag'rikenglikni ta'minlash, chuqur o'ylangan, o'zaro manfaatli va amaliy ruhdagi tashqi siyosat yuritishga yo'naltirilgan davlatimiz mustaqilligi va suverenitetini mustahkamlash, O'zbekistonning yonatrofida xavfsizlik, barqarorlik va ahil qo'shnichilik muhitini shakllantirish, mamlakatimizning xalqaro nufuzini mustahkamlash» [4] deb nomlanib, millatlararo totuvlik munosabatlarini yanada rivojlantirishga ham katta ahamiyat berildi. Albatta, bu yo'nalish nafaqat ichki siyosatga, balki tashqi munosabatlarga ham taaluqli bo'lib, uning asosiy maqsadi — O'zbekistonni xavfsiz, barqaror, ko'p millatli va jahon hamjamiyatida obro'li davlat sifatida rivojlantirishdir. Ayniqsa millatlararo totuvlik va diniy bag'rikenglik borasida amalga oshirilgan ishlar — jamiyatda ijobiy muhit yaratishga va barcha qatlamlarning huquqiy himoyasini ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Yurtimizda, millatlararo totuvlikni mustahkamlash borasida O'zbekistonda yashovchi turli millatlar va etnik guruhlar o'rtasidagi do'stlik va hamkorlikni rivojlantirish maqsadida ko'plab tadbirlar tashkil etildi. “Do'stlik uylari” faoliyati kengaytirilib, milliy-madaniy markazlarning faoliyatiga qo'llab-quvvatlash ko'rsatildi. Har xil millat vakillari o'rtasida o'zaro hurmat va tushunishni mustahkamlashga xizmat qiluvchi madaniy tadbirlar, festivallar va forumlar tashkil qilindi. Bu yo'nalishdagi islohotlar nafaqat ichki barqarorlik va totuvlikni ta'minlashga, balki O'zbekistonni jahon hamjamiyatida ishonchli va nufuzli davlat sifatida ko'rsatishga xizmat qiladi. Ushbu chora-tadbirlar jamiyatda ijobiy muhit yaratish, barcha fuqarolarning huquqlarini himoya qilish va mamlakatning xalqaro maydondagi o'rnini mustahkamlashga katta hissa qo'shib kelmoqda.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, O'zbekistonda millatlararo munosabatlar va bag'rikenglik mamlakatning ijtimoiy-siyosiy barqarorligi va rivojlanishining muhim omillaridan biridir. 2017-2021 yillardagi Rivojlanish Harakatlar Strategiyasi doirasida ushbu sohada muhim islohotlar amalga oshirildi, bu esa turli millatlar va din vakillari o'rtasida o'zaro hurmat, do'stlik va hamkorlikni mustahkamlashga xizmat qildi. “Do'stlik uylari” va milliy-madaniy markazlar faoliyatining kengayishi, diniy erkinlikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan qonunchilik islohotlari, madaniy tadbirlar va ma'rifiy kampaniyalar orqali jamiyatda ijobiy muhit yaratildi. O'zbekistonning tashqi siyosatdagi ochiqlik va pragmatizmga asoslangan yondashuvi mintaqaviy hamkorlikni rivojlantirishga va xalqaro nufuzini oshirishga yordam berdi. Natijada, O'zbekiston ko'p millatli, barqaror va jahon hamjamiyatida nufuzli davlat sifatida o'z o'rnini mustahkamladi, bu esa mamlakatdagi tinchlik va farovonlikni ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyat kasb etdi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES ONLINE

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Annotation: *The rapid development of digital tools has transformed foreign language education, making remote learning more interactive and effective. This article explores modern pedagogical technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), gamification, flipped classrooms, and*

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